

M5live: a historical online environment for electronic music

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***Abstract.** In this paper, we discuss the development of a framework that enables real-time interaction using MUSIC V, the pioneering music synthesis software developed by Max Mathews and ported to modern Gfortran by Bill Schottstaedt and Victor Lazzarini. We seek to generate a collaborative online environment, which allows us not only to disseminate the particularities of this foundational piece of electronic music history but also to extend its logic to the current practices of live-coding and internet music.*

1. Introduction

If ubimus archaeology (a-ubimus) targets the study of past musical experiences through the reconstruction of the musical products and the processes required for their deployment (Radivojević et al., 2022), the recent recovery of the MUSIC V (that enables the synthesis of the earliest examples of computer music code) is a suitable invitation to consider further perspectives of its possible usage. Expanding further on the idea of ubimus-based research, we are not interested in the mere reconstruction of the past artifacts, but in imagining the implications they might have for our creative experience today. In this sense we integrate the replica's source code in an online environment to design our M5live, a platform that on one side examines the questions of preservation of early computer music, and on the other focuses on this seminal, but obsolete piece of music synthesis software as a creative resource.

2. Shaping performativity from media archeology

After the recent opening of the Fonds Jean-Claude Risset (Laboratory PRISM, Marseille) a significant collection of MUSIC V code has been made available for researchers (Tiffon, 2019). Besides being a valuable resource for musicological research, the Fonds collection interrogates us about the possible implications of its content for the creation of today. Recent findings, both of an early MUSIC V source code from Bell Labs (Radivojević et al., 2022) and of sketches of the code for Little Boy, Mutations and other Rissets early experiments (the earliest being dated to 1964, including Computer Study of Trumpet Tones, Microtone Studies, Computer Prelude) provoked our idea to design a framework in which it would be possible to further explore the possibilities of synthesis in MUSIC V.

Lazzarini, Keller, and Radivojević (2022) reported that thanks to the findings in

the Fonds, they could improve MUSIC V version from 2008 (Schottstaedt/Lazzarini), so it is now a functioning replica of the original Bell Lab's MUSIC V written by Max Mathews in 1969. Our M5live is based on the replica's source code.

The main idea behind our M5live is to provide a place for experimentation with the principles of performative archaeology. In examining the salient phenomena of the early computer music creative practices (through the use of the original software), in parallel to the latest concepts of musical interaction and performativity (especially those around live-coding) we focus our ubimus research both on processes and its products.

Our use of the browser as a musical instrument is based not only on its quality as a real-time online compiler but even more as a convergent environment capable of reconstructing diverse code genealogies in a single operational gesture. Thus, we find a potential to develop M5live according to some ubimus pillars, namely: experience-center interaction design, pliability (Keller et al., 2014) extended to remediation, and skeuomorphism.

We can trace certain points of emergence of user interaction by looking at the relationship between access times, technical means, and the objectives resulting from these conditions. For example, in contrast to MUSIC I, in MUSIC III the possibility of dynamic audio parameters arises from BE FAP assembler macros (Lazzarini, 2021). With MUSIC V, the Bell Labs team adds a portable music compiler (Risset, 1985), which allows the control of nested structures.

Whereas the first real-time synthesis program GROOVE was developed by Mathews some years after MUSIC V, the live coding programming history started only a decade later, in Lisp and FORTH (Blackwell & Collins, 2005).

At each stage of the evolution of the electronic music code, the access time between an imaginative gesture, the mathematical translation necessary for its quantification, and its final compilation not only shortens but also increasingly allows a dialectic between a deterministic musical discourse and another more linked to the practice of analog instruments, where the decision-making processes begin to approach the plasticity of the parameters. In HCI terms, the progression of this timeline can be understood as a narrowing of the feedback loop (Norman & Draper, 1986).

The work with the first systems proposed an experience close to the open-loop, due to the type of interface and extended processing times. Thus the reinforcement between the initial proposition and the sound result tended to zero. In the current context of live coding, the code also represents its state (Hieda, 2021) generating loops that bring digital performativity closer to that of analog instruments.

```
INS 0 1 ;
OSC P5 P6 B2 F2 P30 ;
OUT B2 B1 ;
END ;
GEN 0 1 2 0 0 .999 50 .999 285 -.999 306 -.999 461 0 511 ;
NOT 0 1 .50 125 0.45 ;
NOT .75 1 .17 250 0.45 ;
NOT 1.00 2 .50 500 0.46 ;
NOT 1.75 1 .17 1000 0.93 ;
NOT 2.00 1 .95 2000 10.04 ;
NOT 3.00 1 .95 1000 0.45 ;
NOT 4.00 1 .50 500 0.93 ;
NOT 4.75 1 .17 500 0.93 ;
NOT 5.00 1 .50 700 0.93 ;
NOT 5.75 1 .17 1000 13.39 ;
NOT 6.00 1 1.95 2000 12.65 ;
TER 8.00 ;
```

Figure 1. M5live first prototype [m5live.zzt.org]

3. Project goals

Our goal with M5live is to provide a framework of incremental complexity where the serendipitous conditions of musical performance can merge with the methodology and structured thinking of electronic music coding. Using the browser as a musical instrument of genealogical convergence of codes, we can face various political, cultural, and social issues, as well as address the following teleological questions potentially enriching for ubimus studies:

1. Reevaluating an archaeological object through the exploration of its potential future applications. One of these potentialities is its use in collaborative, community-based practice: live-coding. Placing the MUSIC V compiler in a new (and online) environment, allowing for new relations to be explored, we offer open access to a piece of software that was exclusively used by a narrow circle of people in the elitist leading research institutions.
2. Offering us a possibility of re-mediation of live-coding with off-time composing, in both ethical and aesthetical aspects.
3. Making the MUSIC V replica is not restricted only to archaeological benefits in the genesis of early computer works studies. It represents a potential for further artistic and not only scientific research. Acquiring knowledge through artistic practice using our M5live is one of our main concerns. This knowledge is related both to creative resources of the past and to the music performing practices of today.
4. Designing M5live as an environment that could provide a better understanding of

the complexity of early computer music-making through a playful practice-based approach.

5. Potentially developing a methodological tool for performative archaeology, where a reenacted experience of early computer music making is in focus.

4. Initial Technologies

M5live is built by combining various libraries such as ace.js, p5.js, and a simple PHP binder with the original GFortran executables on the backend. Visualizations of envelopes, spectra, and playback of the rendered .wav files are being developed in javascript, p5, and the WebAudio-API.

5. Community based software

Live-coding communities are characterized by sharing not only the programming environments but also the values. This is because the code declaration space equals that of the code practice itself. Thus the concept of a feedback loop also extends to the social sphere. In this sense, our M5live portal will contain online documentation accessible while coding, as well as a repository of Risset's code. Access to historical codes and snippets, including its expandable library of code (for now only Risset's Catalogue, sketches for Little Boy, and Mutations) facilitates MUSIC V learning and exploring the computer music of the past.

We believe that this is a kick-start to generate a community interested in the archaeology of electronic music software and that it could potentially extend to the practices of other pre-Csound experiences. Therefore, the way how the software will be disseminated will depend on the equalization of the feedback loop between MUSIC V and the current HCI experiences. This sensitivity is already present in the founding principles of ubimus, in terms of making a musical practice aware of the historical context, where archaeology appears as a method but also as a sociopolitical decision towards obsolescence and immediate commitment to action of a heritage (Kolody, 2014).

Our platform could potentially be of a pedagogical interest both for the school and universities programs where the history of electronic music could be enriched through an immediate experience of coding in MUSIC V. The dissemination strategies thus are not only limited to the communities closely related to the live-coding, but also for a wider audience.

6. Usage

The interface of M5live resembles that of live-coding, an online editor without further indications, a sidebar with access to files, functions, and support. When the code is executed (pressing CTRL/CMD+ENTER) an instance of m5 is created by sending the MUSIC V code into the interpreter. This can be done with direct raw coding (Figure 2), or by inserting the code on a wrapper (Figure 3).

```
INS 0 1;  
IOS P5 P7 B3 F2 P8;  
END;  
SV2 0 10 2 6 -7;  
SIA 0 4 10000;  
GEN 0 2 1 512 1 1;
```

Figure 2. Default coding style

```
m5 = ["  
  INS 0 1;  
  IOS P5 P7 B3 F2 P8;  
"]
```

Figure 3. Wrapped version

In further developments, wrapping MUSIC V code into a JavaScript closure would allow us to link the output of the MUSIC V with the already mentioned libraries used in M5live, or others related to signal analysis and/or visualization.

To help users in the initials stages of coding in MUSIC V we design a HCI that enables users to see and instantaneously understand the relation between the various parameters and commands by implementing a hover-highlight contextual reference sidebar for each code record. A library of ready-made unit generators and ready-made instruments and orchestras is also provided.

7. Conclusion

Bringing software based on offline synthesis into a live-coding environment may at first sight seem nonsensical. However, many features of M5live that we discussed in this paper make us believe that its unique mingle of off- and in-time properties, joined to the aura of the iconic underlying MUSIC V compiler, can contribute to the creation of a networked environment whose point of discovery is in the first instance ludic. At the same time, M5live may reveal new perspectives on informed musical practices by incrementally accessing awareness of their historical context.

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